

Ritual Sacrifice: An Essential Element Of Ibibio Traditional Religion And Culture

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Abstract:

The reality which religious thoughts express in the diverse religious adherents across the world cannot be over emphasized for instance; sacrificial rite is one of the religious dimensions that occupy a unique place in every religious tradition. This work therefore takes up the challenge to exploy, examine the ritual sacrifice, which is essential element in Ibibio traditional religion. The work shall also look at sacrifice in the three important religions;Christianity, Islam and African Traditional religion. The ritual sacrifice remains the core essence of Ibibio traditional religion and Culture and thus constitutes the essential element of worship. The Ibibio religious Culture is therefore all about ritual sacrifice as families, villages, clan, and communities have their different seasons and time to sacrifice to their God/gods and approach. It concludes by providing the missing link between the living and the dead, the physical and metaphysical, which enhances the attainment of human desires.

Keywords: *Ritual, Sacrifice, Religion, Culture*

Introduction

Dopamu (1985), argues that ever before the Europeans found themselves in Africa, Africans had their ways of life regarding their cultures, religious beliefs and practices, medical systems and other areas of life... He equally submit that even till today when the whole of Africa has equally been infiltrated by western culture and systems, the fact remains that African age old systems still persist enduringly (Dopamu 1985). In similar

but different dimension Olupona (1990), opines that the nature of sacrifice cum ritual and its place in any belief system has always been a central theme of discussion among many scholars especially historians of religion. Mary Douglas, a British anthropologist, describes ritual as a viable means of communication (Douglas 1970). While another anthropologist Victor Turner described sacrifice as formal behavior prescribed for occasions not given over to technological routine that have reference to belief in mystical

beings or power (Turner 1967). In the context of this paper, we owe to Turner the view of sacrifice as a process and to Douglas as a form of communication.

The Ibibio Concept of religion goes synonymously with her concept of sacrifice. As a matter of fact, sacrifice constitutes the essential element in Ibibio traditional religion. The Ibibio, like every other people easily perceive their imperfection, and consequently attain the idea of a perfect being, which is solely responsible for the wonders of creation and the cosmic order, and natural disasters (earthquake, flood, lightning and thunder), rain and sunshine are all enigmatic to the average Ibibio man as he has no specific explanation for them. This then induces him to go in search for more security, long life, wealth and children. Thus, he presupposes the existence of a creator, an eternal order, an “uncaused causer”, in whom all the explanations of the mysteries of creation subsist. It is this being, who is called *Abasi*(God) that created the world, sustains it, provide the order in it, and also accounts for its mysteries nature. For the Ibibio, this being is not alone in His abode. There are other supernatural being which help pilot the affairs of the world and of man in particular. They also believe in the existence of evil or malignant spirit who is continually in hunt for human life in the world. These are called *mfummfumekpo* (The wandering spirit). The Ibibio concept of sacrifice therefore comes

as a result of their continuous search for security in life, and this they believe can be found in only God (*Abasi*). And as a good child, who is always seeing to please the father, when asking for favors, the Ibibio resort to sacrifice to God who is capable of providing their needs. They prefer to loose what is most dear to them in order to please God, so as to receive favours and protection from Him. They believe that by accepting their sacrifice, God is obliged to react to their petitions and thanksgiving. For them, *Abasi* (God) who is faroff cannot be approached directly. Thus, they use the intermediaries of other spirits, deities and divinities, who they believe are nearer to God. They also offer sacrifices to malignant spirit to abate their malicious intervention in human affairs, or to help punish, torment or kill their enemies. The Ibibio understand sacrifice as, ‘A material offering made to God through the intermediaries of spirits, deities and ancestors, with the hope of pleasing them and thereby achieving the desired goal, which can be either positive or negative. Thus, animals are slaughtered, and food and drinks are offered for this purpose. The Ibibio religious culture is therefore all about ritual sacrifice, as families, villages, clans and communities have their different times to offer sacrifice to their gods, God and ancestors, this is done for protection of their kids and kin, families, villages and clans. This paper adopts a phenomenological approach in tackling this problem.

General Concept

In general, sacrifice is understood in two senses the ordinary and the religious sense. Ordinarily understood, it is the gift of oneself or things. It is the voluntary handing away or over of one's person or property for the good of someone else. Rendering of service to another belongs to this category of sacrifice. This goes synonymously with self-denial for the sake of another. This is often termed selfless sacrifice, and has to do with dedicating oneself for a course. A typical example of sacrifice as understood in this sense of voluntary self-offering is the case of Jesus Christ He voluntarily laid down his life for the sake of sinners indiscriminately, that is, for Jews and sacrifice has a religious overtone in the second sense as already noted above. Sacrifice is inherent in all the religions of the world and connotes giving or offering of something precious to God/gods. This designated a ritual sacrifice. Under this sense Arinze (1970), echoes St. Augustine's definition of sacrifice as:

Every work done to effect union with God... a person consecrated to God therefore is a sacrifice, so is our body when chastised with temperance. So is the soul obedient to God. Ritual sacrifices therefore, according to Roland (1961) "The essential act of external worship. It is a prayer which is acted, a symbolic action which expresses both the

interior feelings of the person offering it, and God's response to this prayer... By sacrificial rite, the gift made to God is accepted, union with God is achieved, and the guilty of man is taken away".

Sacrifice may be private or public, internal or external. Public sacrifices are those whose signs and performances are public, and for the good of the community. Such sacrifices are performed during community festivals, such as new yam or masquerade festivals. Private sacrifices on the other hand, are those offered by family heads or individuals, like libation or any other forms of sacrifice made to the family or personal ancestors. External sacrifices have extrinsic signs and performances. Examples of such sacrifices are: festival and coronation sacrifices. Internal sacrifice on the other hand is the internal deposition which accounts for the validity of one's offering as manifested in external sacrifices. Without internal sacrifice therefore, external rites would simply degenerate into formalism, or even magic, as the case may be. In line with this Arinze (1970), described internal sacrifice as "The internal offering of self to God who is our creator/preserver final end... the soul of external sacrifice."

The concept of sacrifice has been treated by two different schools of thought who proposed the two different theories of sacrifice as a communion (communion

theory), and, the oblation and immolation theories of sacrifice. The proponents of the first views hold sacrifice as enhancing communion with the gods and spirits. The second views sacrifice as an offering of something, a sensible thing to portray internal sentiments. Immolation refers to the victim-how it is treated, according to its nature: for example, animals are killed, liquid poured or sprinkled and solid object burnt.

The Concept of Sacrifice in Christian

In the patriarchal era, we read how Cain and Abel sons of Adam and Eve offered sacrifices to the Lord. Cain offered fruits of the field, while Abel immolated the firstlings of flock (Gen. 4:3-6). When Noah stepped out of the Ark after the deluge, he first offered a sacrifice of thanksgiving to God for preserving him and his entire family (Gen. 8:20-22). Again, sacrifices were offered by Abraham, Aaron and Melchizedek. Over all these, God manifested his divine satisfaction, pleasure and wrath, as the case may be. It is noteworthy to point out that Christianity had its origin from Judaism, which constitutes the source of Christian worship as a whole. This is partly because; the leaders of Christianity were all staunch Jews before being converted into Christianity. Even Jesus Christ, the founder of Christianity, was a Jew to the core Himself. However, Christianity did not simply swallow the dogma of Judaism 'look and nail' Thus, there were modifications here and there. It is

these modifications that make the Christian idea of sacrifice significantly different from the Jewish concept, as it is strictly related to the sacrifice of Jesus Christ for the salvation of mankind. This is exactly what is commemorated as communion, as mandated by Christ himself. Christologized and eschatologized.

Christians therefore believe that all other sacrifices of animals and fruits had been pleasing to God only in so far as they pointed to future sacrifice of Christ on the cross. Here Christ is seen as the only victim pleasing to God. He offered himself once and for all on the cross of Calvary, as the ultimate sacrifice ever offered. For Christians, it is the one and the same victim. It is the same Christ who offered Himself today through the administration or officiating of the priest, who once offered himself with a difference only in the mode of offering. When these sacrifices were accompanied by the internal sacrifices of the soul to obedience, contrition and love of God, in anticipation to the redemption wrought by Christ, they prove beneficial to those who offer them. They believe that Christ, a true Lamb of God with unbroken bones, was immolated on the cross for our sake. Jesus, having finished the pasch at last supper therefore instituted the holy sacrifice as the sacrifice of the new law, and ordained his priest to continue to offer his new sacrifice. The Eucharist is therefore the sacrifice of the body and blood of Christ, offered by validly

ordained priest, under the appearances of bread and wine, as a remembrance of the sacrifice of Christ on the cross of Calvary. Christ was thus immolated on the cross, as a possible and mortal man.

In Christendom, the Eucharistic celebration is the effective memorial of the sacrifice of the cross. It is just “a sacrifice and our sacrifice” and is reproduced in the sacramental sacrifice of the Eucharist. “All incomplete and imperfect sacrifices were then replaced by the death of Christ, which fulfilled all the prophecies and realized all the figures” (Onyeocha, 1992). The offering of Christ on the cross remains for Christians, the true sacrifice of the new, the perfect and efficacious sacrifice. It also fulfills the sacrifices of the servant of Isaiah, the lamb of expiation: In summary, Christ is the Priest according to the order of Melchizedek, fulfilling the holocaust of Abraham (Roman 8: 32) the sacrifice of expiation, the evening praise, the inauguration of the new temple (Matt. 21:13; John 2:21). Onyeocha (1992), thus see the Holy Eucharist as a sacrifice and a sacrament. As sacrifice, it has as its object, the glorification of God by adoration, thanksgiving, prayers and expiation. And as a sacrament, it has the sanctification of souls by the bestowal of graces, as its object. On the recipients of the two, he asserts:

The recipients of the sacrament in man, but the recipient of sacrifice is God.

The sacrament bestows merit on the recipient, whereas the sacrifice is the source of both merit and sanctification.

The Concept of Sacrifice in Islam

Generally, Islam means to surrender or submit oneself for obedience to Allah (God). This is very much in line with the general concept of sacrifice noted above. Islam is said to be a revealed religion founded by Mohammed between 610 and 632 AD. In Islam, Mohammed is considered the last of the prophets of Allah (God), the creator of the universe. It first originated in Arabia, and has since spread, even to African continent (like Nigeria). Islam upholds the existence of one unique God (Allah), who is strictly different from created things. He lives eternally, independently of the universe. He is omnipotent and omniscient. In Islam, there is the belief that God will judge the world, and the reward is in paradise or hell. Islam has the Koran for its scriptures.

On ritual sacrifice, Islam shares many insights of the Jews and Christians, though with some marked difference. Though ritual sacrifice does not feature prominently in Islam as in other religions, Akama (1997), identifies the ritual of prayer, one of the five pillars (al Arkans) of Islam as very outstanding. According to Akama:

The procedure of this ritual is a simple one. In all places, whether in the town, on the road or in the bush the devotee goes

through a ritual of ablution. He rolls out his rug or Mat, and bows down towards the holy City of mecca... He offers to Allah (God) less a petition than ascription of praise and declaration of mission to His holy will.

This ritual is performed five times a day, (at dawn, noon, midafternoon, after sunset, and before going to bed). Another important ritual in Islam is the Jumat. This meant specifically for adults, who gather in the Mosque under the leadership of the Imam. It is usually held on Fridays in places where there are pools or fountains, and involves the ablution of the hand, mouth, nostrils, face, fore-arms, neck and feet. Thus, ritual sacrifice in Islam embraces both action and thought. Ritual actions, such as, prayer, fasting and the haji are dominant and obligatory to its adherents (Okaba, 1997).

However, it is to be noted that traditional rites also persist in Islamic form for in the bori spirit possession cult among the Moslem Hausa. The bori here referred to the clan duties of the Hausa. They are guardians of the family compound and personal welfare. They are the main agents of the cause and cure of illness, and as such sacrifices are constantly offered to them. Many people were specially initiated into the bori cult, and these performed colorful public possession dances, exhibited the personality and behavior of the spirits. Their sacrifices therefore constituted

the giving away of food and alms (Kemdirim 1997). Like in African Traditional Religion, Islam also upholds, the practice of divination, and ancestor worship, There is the idea of the supreme God, and the motion of destiny and Judgment. Lew is (1969), observed that all these peripheral cults (of traditional gods) whether condiment or condoned, may be seen to bridge the gap between the moral intensity of traditional personal or social interaction or aspiration, with their customary mystical overtone and the lofty and fantastic concepts. The Muslims therefore have some rituals of the faith, which are performed by their designated priests, such as naming ceremonies, marriages, funerals and public festivals, guiding the ceremonial life of the people in the path of Islamic law and tradition. Again, (Ray, 1976), streamlines two grades of scholars recognized for the performance of Moslem rituals, to include those of the lower grade-the charm seller, who have a little and rudimentary knowledge of the Koran and depend solely upon ritual manipulation of written verses of the Koran which they have been able to memorize. The second grade is the higher grade who study deeply the koranic exegesis and Islamic law and theology at the end of which they receive a certificate called Isnad.

The Concept of Sacrifice in African Traditional Religion

According to Anyanwu (1999), the African, just like any other person easily perceives his imperfection, having seen the mysteries embedded in the world, the world order, and perhaps its hostile nature in human. Consequently, the idea of a supreme being who is responsible for the wonders of creation and the world order as a whole was concerned. Phenomena like; birth, life, death, day and night, natural disasters, rain and sunshine, are all enigmata to the human mind, since he cannot provide any sacrifice explanation to them. This is the origin of African traditional religion, which professes the existence of this Supreme Being, whom man tries to reach through the intermediaries of lesser deities and ancestors.

For Metu (1988), African Traditional religion is strictly linked with rituals, which are expressed in sacrifice, since it is only in sacrifice that the Supreme Being is reached and the gods and lesser divinities, appeased for man's peaceful existence in the world. Ritual sacrifices, therefore are performed for purification, oath taking, prayer, medicine, cure or healing, increased fertility, defeat of enemies, changing of peoples destinies, warding off evil, revealing the future and so on sacrifices are also offered during festivals, and consecration of the living. Awolalu and Dopamu (1979), identify seven categories of sacrifice to include; meal and drink offering,

thanksgiving or gift offering, votive offering, propitiation or expiation offering, substitutionary sacrifices or offering, preventive and foundation sacrifice. Gbenede (1997), also recognized sacrifice as:

One of the elements of worship in which material things like cow, goats, fowls, rice, yam, kolanutsetc, are offered to the supreme Being or through His agents, for good relationship, harmony and communion to heal the wound of trouble and to expect response.

Anyanwu, (1999), apart from the regular and daily worship, Africans offer sacrifice when misfortunes dog their steps when they are asked to offer sacrifices through predictions, oracles, or dreams, or when that want to show gratitude for the blessings which they have received from the divinities. Opoku (1997), identifies objects and designated places for the performance of ritual sacrifices often referred to as shrines to include; family compounds, village squares, thick forests, grooves, caves, bank of rivers and streams, the foot of big and significant tree, the foot of mountains and hills and so on. Kendirim (1997), sees the manner of sacrificial rite in African Traditional religion as descriptive for example, among the Igbo, ritual sacrifice is introduced by the breaking of kola-nut by the cult priest, who offers bit of the kola to the deity, as he invokes the supreme Being (*Chukwu*), the deities,

spirits and ancestor. He addresses directly the deity involved and invites them to commune with the participants by eating what is offer. Thus he asserts:

In fact, in African Traditional religion, every- thing is ritualized – the whole transition of life circle from birth to death, every spectrum of one’s life in tradition is embedded in one form of ritual sacrifice or the other. African Traditional religion therefore is predominantly a religion of rituals and symbols.

Most African culture like the Akans and the Bambutu make offerings of food, especially eggs, wine and meat which they hunt for substance, all for the wellbeing of the people. Hunters like the Ila, make sacrifices when they have no success in hunting, and when the have killed animals. Travellers do so when they come to a river, by offering the water to God, and the river goddess for protection in their journey. The Dinka and the Nuer also have many occasions for sacrifice- for them, every bull, cattle or oxen are destined ultimately for sacrifice. In Africa, animal sacrifices occupy a central place in their religion, and their domestic animals are in their eyes perfect victim. To illustrate this more Mbiti (1969), concludes:

There are sufficient examples to illustrate how African people respond to the

spiritual world through sacrifices and offerings. The items for the sacrifice include; cattles, sheep, goats, chicken, dogs even human being, foodstuff like fruits, maize, mullets, nuts, cassava, vegetable, leaves, honey, eggs, . Beverage, like porridge, milk beer, wine and water... Blood is also offered by a number of societies.

In fact, almost everything that man can get hold of and use is sacrificed to God or spiritual being by one Africa people or another. However all these are accompanied with proper invocation and incantation (prayer) by the properly designated religious functionaries (Priests), as this constitutes the ‘form’ of every efficacious sacrifice in African Traditional religion. This idea indeed, runs through the length and breath of African societies and cultures, as far as sacrifice is concerned.

Theory of Sacrifice as a Religious Act

Here, two French sociologists Henri Hubert and Marcel Mauss (1954), are outstanding. They reached this conclusion having carried out a research on Hindu and Hebrew sacrifices. For them, ‘Sacrifice is a religious act which, through the consecration of a victim modifies the condition of the moral person, who accomplishes it, or that of certain objects with which he is concerned. Like Smith they believed that sacrifice is a sacred

rite, which establish a vital relationship between the sacred and the profane world made possible through the mediation of a ritually sacrificial victim, with a dual function namely; it makes direct contact between the two realms unnecessary as already implied in the mediation. It also has to be noted that through participation in the sacred meals, a God-man relationship is established, (Iffesieh 1989). In their study, it is evident that sacrifice may be performed by individual or a group-family, village, clan, race, and nation, though one person may be selected to act instead of someone or the society. As soon as the priest is chosen and consecrated, he automatically begins some ritual ceremonies to prepare himself for the task ahead – a kind of cleansing ceremonies or rituals. The Hindus belief, that anything that concerns the gods must be sacred or divine. The priest therefore has to be made divine and in fact to become a god himself so that he can exercise meaningful influence upon them. For this reason, like in any other African culture, he has to be cut off from the rest of the world around him for some days before the sacrifice proper. In some cultures, he lives in a special hut prepared for him in the forest and is forbidden from taking part in those normal practices, such as eating certain things, especially meals prepared by women. By this, he has symbolically sacrificed transcendental realm, and as such is fit to perform in the spiritual act of sacrifice. It is then that the religious practice of sacrifice

on behalf of the community begins. However, this long drawn rituals of preparation is only applicable to major and perhaps ceremonies of exceptional gravity (clan or village feasts for instance). Since sacrifice entails interaction with the sacred, the priest who is imperfect, must enter gradually through recommended rituals into the sacred spheres which is traditional and recognized abode of the gods (Omeje, 1981).

Conclusion

The organization of sacrificial rites in the different cultures and religions has undoubtedly been influence by a number factor. Economic consideration, for example, certainly have had some impact upon primitive peoples in the selection of the victim and the time of sacrifice and in the determination of whether the victim is consumed or totally destroyed and whether the sacrifice is an individual or a collective group. The importance of such factor is an aspect of sacrifice that deserves increased investigation.

Nevertheless, sacrifice is not a phenomenon that can be reduced to national terms; it is fundamentally a religious act that has been of profound significance to individuals and social groups throughout history, a symbolic act that established a relationship between man and the sacred order. For many people of the world,

throughout time, sacrifice has been the very heart of their religious life.

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